

Palladium (II) Complexes of α -Oximinoacetetarylamide Semicarbazones

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Semicarbazones of a number of Palladium(II) complexes of the type, Pd(OAAS)₂ where, OAAS represents α -oximinoacetoacetanilide; *o*-toluidide; *p*-toluidide; *o*-chloroanilide; *m*-chloroanilide; *p*-chloro-anilide; *o*-anisidide; *p*-anisidide; (2,4)-xylylide; (2,4)-dimethoxyanilide; and *p*-phenitidide have been prepared. The infrared and electronic spectra of the ligands, and infrared spectra and magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes have been studied. All the complexes are diamagnetic and their infrared spectra suggest the coordination of these ligands through nitrogens of the oximino and semicarbazide moieties. The square planar stereochemistry around the Pd(II) ion in the complexes have been proposed.

THE synthesis of semicarbazones of α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide¹ and analytical aspects of some of these with Palladium have been reported². The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of Palladium (II) complexes with α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide semicarbazones.

Experimental

Apparatus: The magnetic susceptibilities of the Pd(II) complexes were determined at room temperature by the Gouy method, using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a calibrant. Infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes in KBr discs were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss UR-10

Spectrophotometer fitted with LiF, NaCl and KBr prisms. The electronic spectra of the ligands in ethanol solution ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$) were measured on Beckman DU Spectrophotometer.

Materials used: Palladium chloride (Johnson, Matthey & Co., London) and ethyl alcohol, purified by refluxing with 2% sodium hydroxide and 2% zinc dust followed by distillation were used.

Preparation of the complexes: 10 ml. aq. solution of Pd(II) chloride (0.05M) was gradually added to 25 ml. alcoholic solution (2%) of α -oximinoacetoacet-

TABLE I—PALLADIUM COMPLEXES OF α -OXIMINOACETOACETARYLAMIDE SEMICARBAZONES

No.	R	Composition	Colour	m. p. (decomp.)	% Palladium		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₁₀ Pd	Bright yellow	268	17.12	16.92	22.30	22.20*
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₁₀ Pd	golden yellow	265	16.10	16.20	21.24	21.25*
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₁₀ Pd	"	270	16.12	16.20	21.30	21.25
4.	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₁₀ Cl ₂ Pd	Bright yellow	280	15.12	15.25	19.95	20.01
5.	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₁₀ Cl ₂ Pd	"	268	15.16	15.25	20.20	20.01
6.	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₁₀ Cl ₂ Pd	Golden yellow	270	15.22	15.25	19.90	20.01
7.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₁₀ Pd	Orange yellow	265	15.50	15.45	20.20	20.27
8.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₁₀ Pd	Red	267	15.37	15.45	20.30	20.27
9.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ O ₆ N ₁₀ Pd	Golden yellow	360	15.42	15.54	20.45	20.38
10.	2,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ O ₁₀ N ₁₀ Pd	Red	259	14.09	14.21	18.63	18.65
11.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ O ₈ N ₁₀ Pd	Red	263	15.02	14.85	19.42	19.48

*For Correspondence

chloroanilide semicarbazone and acidified with dil. HCl. The mixture was diluted to about 100 ml. with distilled water and digested on waterbath for half an hour; the bright yellow precipitates obtained were filtered; washed with hot water and aq. ethanol (1 : 1), and dried in an oven at 110°.

The Pd(II) complexes of the other α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide semicarbazones of the series were prepared in the same manner.

The m. p., colour, elemental analysis and composition of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Electronic spectra of the ligands: The chromophoric system $\text{N}=\text{C}-\overset{\text{N}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ in the ligands exhibits

a band at λ_{max} 260-65 nm, and molar extinction coefficients 20600-26800 (Table 2). Comparison of these spectra with those of acetoacetarylamide semicarbazones with chromophoric system, $\text{N}=\text{C}-\overset{\text{H}}{\mid}{\text{C}}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ (λ_{max} 230-250 nm; $\epsilon=15000$ to 22900)⁸ reveals that there is a bathochromic displacement to the extent of 11-35 nm with the hyperchromic effect ($\Delta\epsilon=2000-9000$). This is in good agreement with the generalisation of Braude⁴.

TABLE 2—UV SPECTRA OF α -OXIMINOACETOACETARYLAMIDE SEMICARBAZONES

No.	R	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}
1.	H	260	23300
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	264	20800
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	260	23300
4.	<i>o</i> -Cl	263	22800
5.	<i>m</i> -Cl	264	23500
6.	<i>p</i> -Cl	264	25100
7.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	265	21400
8.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	265	25400
9.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	265	20600
10.	2,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	265	25400
11.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	260	26800

Magnetic susceptibility: All the Pd(II) complexes were found to be diamagnetic. Hence the square planar structure for all the complexes has been suggested.

Infrared spectra: Insolubility of the Pd(II) complexes in organic solvents precluded conductivity, molecular weight, NMR and electronic spectral measurements. The information about the structure of the complexes has been derived from the infrared data of the ligands and complexes.

The important infrared spectral bands and their assignments (Table 3) are based on the study of the free ligands and Pd(II) complexes. The strong band at 3450-3520 cm⁻¹ appears in the ligands but does not appear in the corresponding complexes. This suggests the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bond in the ligands. This band is within the expected region for intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁵. The absence of such band in the complexes is the indication of the replacement of hydrogen of oximino group by metal ion. The strong band at 970-95 cm⁻¹ in the ligands is attributed to N-O stretch. In the complexes this band shifts to 1130-80 cm⁻¹. The N-O stretches of nitrogen and oxygen coordinated oximino groups are expected to shift to higher and lower frequencies respectively compared to that of the ligands. The increase in N-O frequency shows the coordination through nitrogen of oximino group. This further agrees with the usual behaviour of oxime group to coordinate through nitrogen atom⁶⁻⁹. According to Sterk and Ziegler ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$, 1625 cm⁻¹)¹⁰, the strong band around 1590-1615 cm⁻¹ in the ligands indicates C=N stretching frequency. In the complexes this band appears around 1580-1605 cm⁻¹. The lowering of the C=N stretching frequency is an indication of the coordination of semicarbazide and oximino nitrogen atoms. The infrared spectra of

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TABLE 3—IMPORTANT INFRARED BANDS OF LIGANDS AND THEIR PD(II) COMPLEXES (CM⁻¹)

No.	νC=N	νN-O	νOH	νNH			νC=O		
				Free	Primary Assoc.	Secondary Assoc.	Amide-I	Amide-II	Amide-III
1	1595 s	970 s	3480 sb	3400 w	3130 w	3360 s	1640 s 1670	1560 s	1270 s, 1300 s
1A	1590 s	1140 m	—	3420 s	3110 w, 3210	3320 s	1660 s, 1680	1560 s	1330 s
2	1615 s	985 s	3460 b	—	3200 sb, 3250 sb	3350 sb	1655 s, 1670 s	1540 s	1280 s
2A	1590 s	1170 s	—	3420 sb	3060 w, 3170 w, 3210 s	3300 sb	1650 s, 1680 s	1550 s	1290 s
3	1600 s	995	3450 sb	3500 w	3070 w, 3120 s 3200	3300 s	1655 s, 1680 s	1550 sb	1265 s, 1300 s
3A	1580 s	1180 s	—	3430 s, 3390 s	3195 s, 3210 s	3320 sb	1655 s, 1680 s	1550 s	1295 s
4	1590 s	990 s	3510 vs	3400 vs	3080 w, 3140 w 3190 w	3340 s	1640 s, 1670 s	1560 m	1295 s
4A	1580 s	1180 s	—	3430 sb, 3390 w	3200 s	3300 s	1660 s, 1680 s	1540 s	1310 s
5	1595 s	985 s	3460 sb	—	3060 w, 3110 w, 3190	3300 sb	1660 s, 1680 s	1535 s	1280 s, 1305 s
5A	1580 s	1130 sh	—	3430 s	3060 sb, 3190 w 3210 s	3320 s	1660 s, 1700 s	1555 s	1260 w, 1305 s
6	1600 s	995 s	3460 sb	3410 w	3060 w, 3130 s, 3200	3300 s	1660 s, 1680 s	1550 s	1260 m, 1295 s
6A	1585 s	1180 s	—	3410 w, 3490	3200 sb	3300 s	1665 s, 1690 s	1545 s	1305 s
7	1595 s	995 s	3460 sb	—	3200 sb	3330 s	1660 s, 1690 s	1550 s	1260 s, 1290 m
7A	1590 s	1175 s	—	3400 sb	3200 s	3300 s	1660 s, 1690 s	1550 s	1255 s, 1280 m
8	1605 s	985 s	3450 vs	3380 w	3200 w	3300 s	1660 s, 1690	1550 s	1280 m, 1305 s
8A	1595 s	1160 s	—	3420 sb	3210 s	3320 s	1660 s, 1690 s	1550 s	1300 s
9	1610 s	980 s	3470 sb	—	3060 w, 3130 s	3300 sb	1680 s, 1700 s	1540 s	1290 s
9A	1590 s	1170 s	—	3430 s	3110 w, 3210 s	3300 s	1660 s, 1700 s	1560 s	1290 s
10	1615 s	990 s	3520 sb	3460 m	3130 w, 3200 sb	3300 w	1660 s, 1700 s	1550 s	1270 s, 1295 s
10A	1605 s	1180 m	—	3420 s	3120 w, 3210 sb	3300 sb	1655 s, 1690 s	1540 s	1305 s
11	1605 s	990 s	3470	3490 s	3110 sb, 3200 m	3300 sb	1650 s, 1695 s	1550 s	1280 s, 1305 m
11A	1600 s	1170 s	—	3410 sb	3050 w, 3210 s	3320 s	1660 s, 1695 s	1550 s	1300 s

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak, b=broad, vs=very strong, sh=shoulder.

Serial numbers are according to Table—1 and with letter A are the corresponding complexes.

the ligands and complexes reveal bands of strong, medium or weak intensity around $3050-3250\text{ cm}^{-1}$, 3300 cm^{-1} and two around 3400 and 3500 cm^{-1} indicating primary association, secondary trans association and free NH vibrations of amides respectively¹¹.

From the spectra (Table 3) it is evident that ligands as well as complexes in the solid state are mostly in the associated form. The probable associations are due to hydrogen bonding between carbonyl groups and hydrogens of the amide and semicarbazide moieties. The strong band around 3300 cm^{-1} is considered to be due to trans associated form (Structure 1). The strong bands in the ligands and complexes around 1650 and 1690 cm^{-1} , 1550 cm^{-1} , and 1200 and 1300 cm^{-1} are attributed to amide I, amide II and amide III bands respectively¹¹.

From the foregoing elemental analysis, magnetic measurements and spectral data the structure has been proposed for the complexes. (Structure 1).

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